

Importance of Nursing – A Review

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Abstract

Health Care plays a vital role in our day to day life; to make it clear health industry has to be always dynamic, with medical breakthrough every day to stay ahead not only in advanced technologies but also in education, training, performance and monitoring. It is most important aspect of life changer in Nursing. Environment for nurses should be safe endowing and sustaining to improve health care for all. Nursing quality plays an important aspect of patient health care. All nurses should promote ethical competence. In this review paper importance of nursing such as work environment for nurses, nursing quality, ethics, innovation are discussed.

Keywords: Terms; Nursing; Patient Care; Intensive Care

Introduction

Nursing plays very vital role in health care because their concentration lies in patient care. They work in various specialties to recuperate patient's health and to prevent injuries and illness [1]. To be more precise, nurses are always in the front line of health care. They blend principles of health services with the art of caring to provide patient comfort and recovery. Apart from all these, nurses also aid as patient advocates, health educators and coordinators of different health care services. Services of nurses are in a wide variety including offices, adult facilities, prisons, private clinics and also in military. Responsibilities of nurses extend to person's life from cradle to grave. They not only follow doctor's instructions but also make sure that patient receives high quality care in an organized and ethical manner. This is one of the reason educations for nursing is a continuous journey that does not end even after completing four year nursing program [2].

Figure 1: Illustrates Nurse accessing patient's information through transparent touch screen [3].

Work Environment for Nurses

Nurses must have a healthy work environment that is safe, empowering and sustaining in order to lead the way in improving health and health care for all [4]. As per US

Department of Health and human Services working conditions of nurses and their relationship leads to patient safety. There were two major working conditions that were identified:

- 1) Key features of the work environment for nurses that likely to have a significant impact on patient safety.
- 2) If working environment is healthy and with potential improvements in working conditions then there would be more likely increase patient's safety [5].

Improving the working conditions involves

- a) Defining the choice of nursing practice so that nurses can work to their full potential for patient care
- b) Ensuring that nurse voice is heard, having access to decision making bodies
- c) Ensuring that other disciplines are implemented in the development of policies for safe work environments
- d) Presenting awards to health care facilities that demonstrates the positive working environments, reduced dropout rates, public opinion, improved care and patient satisfaction [6].

Figure 2: Illustrates nursing professional practice model [7].

Nursing Quality

Nursing quality plays vital role in nursing care – they are structure, process and its outcomes. Structural indicators include the resource of nursing staff, level of skill, education and certification levels of nursing staff. Process indicates estimation methods of patient assessments and nursing interventions. Nursing job well-being is also considered a process indicator. Outcome indicators demonstrates patient outcomes that are calculated to be nursing-sensitive because they depend on the quantity and quality of nursing care.

Taking it further below are the important factors that are considered: [8]

- a) Patient satisfaction with pain management
- b) Patient satisfaction with nursing care
- c) Patient satisfaction with overall care
- d) Patient satisfaction with medical information provided
- e) Nurse Job satisfaction

Figure 3: Illustrates nursing professional practice model [9].

Ethics

Ethics in nurses are the most important aspect of the nursing and its development. Ethics and Human Rights was made to aid nurses navigate ethical value conflicts, life and death decisions. It was designed to address any issues in ethics and human rights at the state, national and international levels. It should promote ethical competence and human rights sensitivity of nurses in all practice and continuing commitment to human rights [10].

Figure 4: Illustrates nursing Ethics practice model [11].

Advocacy in Nursing

Advocacy in nursing is backbone of nursing. Nurses should advocate for their patients not only in the workplaces, in their communities but also in legislative and political advocacy is very crucial for advancing the profession and patient care.

Innovation in Nursing

Every nurse is a promotor of positive change and an innovator. Every day, nurses work together to resolve difficult problems in the workplace and for their patients. The goal is always same: better care [13]

Four takeaways from innovation in nursing field are:

- e) Patient-centered care
- f) Post remission support
- g) Nurses in user-experience roles
- h) Automating and streamlining work process [14]

Take Away on Future of Nursing

Below are take away on future of nursing are –

- i) Nurses should perform to the full extent of their education and training
- j) Nurses should attain higher levels of education and training through improved system that provides seamless academic progression
- k) Nurses should be full compliance with physicians and other health care professionals in redesigning health care system
- l) Effective and efficient workforce planning and policy making should be always improved
- m) Broaden opportunities for nurses to lead collaborative improvement efforts.
- n) Carry out nurse residency programs
- o) Ensuring that nurses are engaged in lifelong learning
- p) Provide and allow nurses to lead change to advance health care [16].

Conclusion

This review article characterizes about the nursing and its characteristics such as work environments for nurses, nursing quality, innovation in nursing. It delineates that how nursing quality can innovation can be improved based on the innovation, ethics and technology.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest as per author's point of view.

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